

The Contribution of Cattle Fattening to the Improvement of the Living Conditions of Households in the Village of Konna (Mopti)

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to analyse the impact of the practice of cattle fattening on the live conditions of the populations in the village of Konna (Mopti).

One hundred and thirty one (131) cattle fatteners were interviewed based on a questionnaire focusing mainly on the conduct of the fattening activity; the constraints encountered and the impact of the fattening activity on the living conditions of the respondents, including observations in the field. A descriptive analysis is made with the analysis software SPSS-18 has shown that 95 (72.5%) men against 26 (27.5%) women practice cattle fattening activity. Respondents encounter some difficulties; only 16% benefited from loans from financial institutions. Cattle rationing is mixed, the most used feeds being brown cake (90.8%) and rice bran (85.5%). The acquisition of veterinary products is done on the local market (83.2%), itinerant merchants (6.9%) and ordered from outside (9.9%). The aim of the cattle fattening activity is to increase the pecuniary income for a better living condition. We witness that out of the 131 respondents 31, 3% were able to cover their medical expenses; 26.7% were able to pay for school supplies for their children; 10.7% were able to pay their rent; 67.2% saw an improvement in their food; 24.4% were able to carry out other income generating activities; 15.3% had access to drinking water; 13.7% had access to electricity, and about 23.7% of respondents sleep under an impregnated mosquito net.

KEYWORDS: Cattle fattening, Household, Konna

INTRODUCTION

Due to global population growth, the problem of nutrition is also a problem for both developed and developing countries, such as Mali. A balanced diet and an adequate intake of animal proteins have become a priority issue for all countries. As a result, the livestock sector has retained its strategic importance despite the development of technology and industrialization policies (Serap GÖNCÜ, 2019). Studies have shown that the increase in population causes the demand for the number of animals and the production of red meat. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), red meat contains nutritional factors that are very valuable for human health.

Animal husbandry is the second most practiced activity in Konna after agriculture. This primary sector of the economy plays an important part in the life of a nation, and an essential role in the economy of a country like Mali. Faced with the security crisis prevailing in the Mopti region, and the lack of income-generating activity in the village, would cattle

fattening be a boon for the population of the village of Konna?

The country's strategic position in the heart of West Africa gives it a particular importance in the supply of cattle and meat to neighbouring countries; namely Côte d'Ivoire and Senegal and some coastal countries (Ghana and Nigeria). The livestock trade is an important economic activity that has historically linked Sahelian countries such as Mali, Burkina Faso, Niger and Senegal to the countries of the wetter coastal zone (Côte d'Ivoire, Ghana, Nigeria). Livestock exports from Mali and other Sahelian countries in the regional livestock trade are thriving year on year. It is a sector that generates jobs and raw materials (hides, horns,...).

In 2017, according to the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), Mali exported 207,266 cattle, 358,829 sheep, 34,244 goats, 1,614 horses, 1,190 donkeys, 7,702 camels, and 440 pigs. Cattle occupy the 2nd place numerically among ruminants. Most of these animals are reared in the extensive traditional system, which includes transhumant and sedentary systems. Semiintensive and

“The Contribution of Cattle Fattening to the Improvement of the Living Conditions of Households in the Village of Konna (Mopti)”

intensive systems require more or less investment in inputs, labour and infrastructure. The latter types of systems are practiced in peri-urban areas, urban areas and in specialized workshops. It is estimated that only 4.2% of cattle are affected by these systems. So we can see that the production of cattle meat comes almost entirely from the extensive system. The production of livestock meat in the intensive system is mainly destined for export.

Indeed, with the increasing demand for animal products including meat, skins, and manure due to urbanization, and the increase in incomes and population, extensive traditional methods characterized by low animal productivity are no longer able to meet the needs of the population. This would explain the emerging interest in the practice of cattle fattening in urban and peri-urban areas. Aware of the interest and importance of this activity for the country, the Malian government, through programs and projects such as the Support Project for the Development of Livestock in the Mopti Region (PADEM), has decided to provide financial support to the promoters. These programs and projects will enable the beneficiaries to improve their profession through better management of livestock activities and also their living conditions. These various programmes and projects will increase the competitiveness and profitability of the livestock-meat sector in the region while meeting the requirements of regional and sub-regional markets. Although several people fatten cattle, technical information about the activity is scarce or non-existent for the population of Konna. Therefore, the low technical skills of the breeders are often the cause of lower performance, as well as significant losses that can be recorded due to a lack of adequate training. There are various technologies for meat production, in the form of data sheets, but their use is limited due to several factors; including the lack of extension and the illiteracy of the population. Hence; the need to know the production capacity of fattening units and the obstacles to cope with the ever-increasing demand for animal products in the region and even in Mali.

This study focuses on cattle fattening in the village of Konna. According to a government study carried out in the area, cattle occupy the first place among ruminants; 60013 cattle in 2016 followed by sheep, goats, donkeys, horses, camels, and poultry; (PRRE 2018). This herd supplies the whole commune with meat, milk and derivatives (cooking, skins, etc.).

The increase in demand at the national level, and neighbouring countries for red meat is due to the increase in population. According to many authors, livestock farming is an economic activity that reduces poverty and provides a guarantee for herders in the event of poor harvests.

The study is devoted to semi-intensive fattening. The purpose of this study is to analyse the practice of cattle fattening in the village of Konna in order to measure the contribution of this

activity to the lives of the population. It is also a question of detecting the various difficulties and weaknesses that fatteners face.

1. The practice of cattle fattening in Konna

1.1 Overview of the livestock sector in Mali

Livestock farming is a key sector in the socio-economic life of the population and contributes substantially to the country's economy. It directly helps millions of marginalized and vulnerable people earn a living. According to the ministry in charge, its contribution to the national GDP was 15.2%, second only to agriculture (16.2%) in 2013. It employs about 80% of the rural population and is an important source of livelihood for the latter, according to the same source. In addition, livestock farming plays an important role in the life of the working population. It contributes to the improvement of living conditions through food and nutrition security, access to basic social services, the reduction of unemployment and poverty in general.

According to the Ministry in 2008, the total added value produced by the meat sector at the marketing stage is 115,332 million CFA francs, including 49,747 million CFA francs for cattle, 14,836 million CFA francs for sheep, 11,600,273,000 CFA francs for goats, 1,476 million CFA francs for camels and 37,671 million CFA francs for poultry. This represents more than 19% of the national value added according to the same source.

Livestock products are the third largest export after cotton and gold, with a value of more than 744 billion CFA francs (MEP, 2008). The development of the livestock sector is important as a factor in poverty reduction. In 2015 according to the annual report of the Ministry of Livestock and Fisheries (ANNUAL REPORT 2015), the herd consisted of 10,622,620 cattle, 15,143,415 sheep, 21,087,150 goats, 538,545 horses, 979,510 donkeys, 1,008,440 camels, and 82,425 pigs. These herds are consumed within the country and also imported outside the country.

1.2 Definitions and Types of Fattening

For several years, a large part of the population of Konna has been engaged in an activity called fattening. Fattening is designed as an intensive rearing technique practiced on lean cattle kept in stalls and aimed at producing meat in a relatively short time. It consists of fattening and conditioning certain types of livestock for slaughter, usually cattle and cows. Animals are bought based on how thin they are. Most fattening animals have already reached full skeletal size (Metzel and Doumbia 1998). This technique therefore involves fattening, which is none other than an increase in body mass with a more or less important proportion of adipose deposition (DEZLY, 2016). In short, fattening is the business of buying healthy animals, feeding and fattening

them to optimal carcass weight, and selling them at any time of the year.

We assist with different types of fattening, namely: the first type of fattening is called; grassy fattening or extensive fattening. This type of fattening consists of maintaining the animals on natural or cultivated pastures. Only mineral supplementation is given. This is the method used in ranching. The second type of fattening is called; Extensive fattening mainly concerns young animals in cattle (2 to 5 years of age). It is usually done over 1 to 2 years covering two rainy seasons (DEZLY, 2016). The third type of fattening is semi-intensive fattening, also known as peasant fattening. It consists of buying or taking a certain number of lean head from one's herd in order to fatten it up within a relatively long period of time (3-5 months) in order to sell for an income.

Finally, the last type of fattening, known as intensive or industrial fattening, is mainly devoted to livestock traders and breeders with farms in peri-urban areas. Feeders are the main buyers of cattle. Their mouthed cattle are destined for export (H. SANON et al. 2014).

The main objective of the fattening operation is to achieve the highest live weight in the shortest possible time, in the most economical way.

All the types of fattening mentioned above are practiced in the village of Konna; However, the most common is semi-intensive fattening. It is very popular nowadays because all strata practice there (young people, women, men, civil servants, etc.) as well as all ethnic groups. Cattle fattening is a very lucrative business in the Mopti region, particularly in the village of Konna.

1.3 Cattle fattening in Konna

Cattle farming; is an important and highly prized livestock production sector and plays an important role in the village economy. Generally, before starting the cattle fattening business, the farmer should know the type of finished product he wants, the time it takes to produce it, and the income he expects to earn from the sale of his livestock. Depending on these objectives, he will decide both the breed and category of cattle to be fattened and also the type of fattening to be practiced according to DEZLY (2016). Mouthed cattle are chosen according to their breed, age, color, and sex. This is because unneutered males are more stressed because females are smaller and are usually slaughtered than when they are significantly older. Black cattle are avoided for psychological reasons.

Among the practitioners, some take oxen or lean cows from their herd and put them in a pen to feed them for a certain period of time. This is for the purpose of selling them or returning them to their herd. During this breeding period, the cattle are dewormed, fed with meal, bran and other feed. On the other hand, other practitioners buy the lean cattle they fatten in order to sell for a profit. For this second practice of

fattening, the cattle are dewormed, stall and monitored regularly by veterinarians. In the village of Konna, the majority of fatteners are made up of the latter category of fattening. Feeders face some loads, but feed costs are the main source of expense for the business. Generally, all the cattle are sold in the local market, much of it during the month of Ramadan. This sales operation during the month of Ramadan is carried out as follows: for the feast of Ramadan, Muslim households organize themselves into groups of ten, fifteen or more; to slaughter livestock. The majority of fatteners are men, despite the low representation of women who do not have financial means. It is important to emphasize that the activity of cattle fattening is practiced throughout the year, but most fatteners take advantage of the cold season because; At this time of year, livestock are cheaper, the climate is favourable, and feed for livestock rationing is cheaper. The price of cattle increases throughout the fattening period until June or even July. The price is due to the fact that the largest sales of animals in Mali occur during the dry and cold season (Metzel and Doumbia 1998). The cattle are housed in buildings constructed of wood, banco or cinder blocks. The infrastructure built for the activity is enclosed, well ventilated, and wide and clean (to avoid developing parasitic and contagious diseases).

The hayloft; A storage infrastructure for fodder to be used to feed the cattle that are fed is installed for the proper practice of the activity. It makes it possible to build up fodder stocks and thus promote the planning of fattening operations over time. The hayloft also makes it possible to carry out the fattening activity even in the dry season when there is a huge lack of fodder in the area. The construction of a hayloft must comply with certain standards to avoid termite attacks, good air circulation, and better control of feed stock (DEZLY, 2016).

To cover all the needs of the activity throughout the operation and to avoid very damaging stock shortages, the fatteners in the village of Konna are building up provisional stocks of feed: fodder, concentrates, minerals, straw, bran, etc.). Feeders, drinking troughs, and other utensils (buckets, empty drums, basins, etc.) are used for the distribution of feed in the barn. Since there is no machine for food preparation, everything is set up manually by the fatteners. For the proper conduct of the fattening operation, the health of the animals must be controlled, in the same way as the feeding, in order to meet the conditions for its profitability. It is for this reason that the feeders focus on veterinary services. These veterinary services can be quarantine, deworming, vaccination, various care, etc.

The net profit that a fattener can make from its activity is determined by the difference between its overall revenue (all its sales) and its total expenses (fixed and variable costs). In order to maximize its profit, the fattener increases its sales, reduces its expenses, or a combination of both. If the fattener

does not know precisely its expenses, (production costs) its ability to increase its profit will be very low.

2. THE CONTRIBUTION OF FATTENING TO THE LIVING CONDITIONS OF HOUSEHOLDS

Generally speaking, the sale of livestock makes it possible to solve the family's expenses in the face of different needs, according to Alassane Bah (2011). The practice of cattle fattening has an influence on the price of meat and also on the exploitation of some by-products (hides, manure, and cooking) Malick GAYE (2000). The income from fattening allows the fatteners to carry out other income-generating activities (sale of condiments, snacks, etc.) as well as to deal with certain social cases (baptism, marriage, circumcision, etc.). This income allows some feeders to pay for their children's schooling, health care and food needs. The authors Fatimata DIA and Aminata BADIANE (1998) argue that fattening revenues make it possible to compensate for expenses that agricultural incomes have not been able to sustain because of rainfall or other climatic hazards. According to Escot (2011), meat from cattle that has been mouthed is fatter, heavier, more tender, attracts customers, is beautiful to see by customers and brings more profit. The same author goes on to say that mouthed meat is easier to sell than unmouthed meat. The customers of mouthed meat are not only private individuals, but also hotels and restaurants. In addition to the quality of the meat, all religious denominations consume meat from cattle fattening. Manure from cattle that have been fed is an important factor in production for farmers. It is a natural, high-quality agricultural input. Many farmers are unable to source chemical Einkorns. Manure (organic manure) significantly increases farmers' yields.

In addition to the sale of meat, the fattening of cows has the possibility of setting up small dairy units. For those who practice this type of cattle fattening, a new source of income creation is emerging. This is the availability of milk for the population in the dry season. According to researchers Covarrubias, Nsiima, and Zezza (2012); In Tanzania, three out of five households report that 20 percent of their income comes from animal husbandry, in addition to organic manure and animal traction. These households also benefit from a much higher consumption of animal products. Livestock production not only improves the nutritional status of the population, but also, and above all, provides income to several segments of the population through trade (ECOWAS, 2008). Cattle fattening in cities is an additional source of income for people working in jobs other than farming. The practice of cattle fattening enables rural households to cope with income poverty, food and nutrition insecurity, as well as underemployment and access to basic social services.

3. STUDY MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

3.1 Study Site

The rural municipality of Konna is made up of 28 villages. As for the village of Konna, it is located on the national road, RN 16 (Sévare-Gao); 55 km north of Sévaré and 65 km from Mopti and 45 km south of Lake Korientzé. The commune of Konna is between two circles to the east, the circle of Douentza and the circle of Bandiagara (commune of Dangol Bore; and the communes of Lowel Gueou and Pignari), to the west by the commune of Dialloubé; to the north by the Commune of Ouroubè – Doudè and to the south by the Commune of Borondougou. The north-west of Konna is flooded while the east is flooded. The flooded area is crossed by the Niger River, which is navigable for 40 km at any time of the year. The river is also fed by rainwater runoff from the Dogon plateau (PRRE 2018). The climate of the Commune of Konna is of the Sudano-Sahelian type. The temperature differences between the hot day and the cool night are between 20° and 45°C. This climate is characterized by early or late rains and often droughts after the first rains. Cumulative rainfall varies between 250 and 450 mm and is unevenly distributed over time and space (MDREPDESC, 2016).

According to the Ministry of Economy and Finance (MEF), in 2016 the population of the village of Konna is estimated at about 16,000 inhabitants out of the 49,966 inhabitants (CHAHIRA 2013) that make up the commune. According to the source, the village is made up of Fulani, Marka, Bozo, Bambara, Somono, Rimaïbés, Malinkes, Dogon, Sonrhaï etc. All its ethnic groups practice livestock farming as an income-generating activity (IGA). The vegetation is predominated by shrubs and herbaceous plants. The forest of Sassimba is located in the Commune. The flora consists of thorns (*Acacia albida*, *Acacia seyal*, *Acacia nilotica*, *Acacia radiana*, *Cacia siyamina*, *Cacia siberiyana*, *Balanites egyptiaca*, *Jujuphis mauriatiana*), *Combretacés* (*Combretum migratum*, *Guiera senegalensis*, *Combretum glitinosum*, etc.), *Ronier* (*Boracis flaberiphera*), *Baobab*, *Tamarindus indica*, *Diospiros*, *Parkia biglobosa*, *Pourparcias béréa*, etc. (MDRE-PDESC, 2016).

3.2 The methodological approach

The methodological approach of the study consisted in developing a survey sheet to collect qualitative data and also observations from fatteners in the village of Konna. The study population consists of people engaged in activities other than cattle fattening. It is pointed out that all the respondents reside in the village of Konna. The 131 respondents represent all categories of the population (young, adult, man, woman, old) including the ethnic groups of the village of Konna.

Two young graduates are in charge of carrying out this survey through cards drawn up in the village of Konna. These various collected data are codified, entered and analyzed with the SPSS-18 software. The study population consists of cattle

“The Contribution of Cattle Fattening to the Improvement of the Living Conditions of Households in the Village of Konna (Mopti)”

fatteners (men and women) in the village of Konna. For a more coherent analysis, the survey involved 131 randomly selected people of all genders and statuses (occupation and marital). All age categories are affected. This surveyed population carries out all the activities carried out in Konna; trade, agriculture, livestock, market gardening, etc. A survey sheet has been drawn up with five main axes: general information on the farmer, the conduct of the fattening activity (animals, feeding, veterinary products), the price of livestock, the constraints encountered and the impact of the activity on the lives of the respondents. All 131 feeders have been opened and available for investigation. During these surveys, observations and measurements were made on the available infrastructure and equipment.

4. DATA ANALYSIS

Structure, driving and fattener performance variables were selected for classification analyses. Descriptive and frequency analysis were applied to determine the extent to which the different variables were related. Descriptive statistics (averages, percentage) and analyses of variance were carried out to characterize the classes of feeder farms obtained in the area.

5. INTERPRETATION OF THE RESULTS

To fully understand the subject, the interpretation of the data will focus on four main parts, namely: the socio-economic situation of feeders; the characteristics of bovine fattening; the constraints related to the practice of the activity of cattle fattening and its impact on the living conditions of the fatteners

5.1. Discussion

The analysis shows that cattle fattening in Konna is the prerogative of men. Of the 131 of the population surveyed; 95 are men (72.5%) compared to 36 women (27.5%). Table 1 shows the profile of the fatteners; these are; gender, age, occupation, and educational attainment. The results show that the majority of respondents are young people under the age of 30, i.e. 61 of the respondents (46.6%), followed by those between the ages of 31 and 40 (24.4%). Adults account for 23.7% and pensioners 5.3%. Thus, it can be seen that all categories of people practice cattle fattening for various reasons. Among them, livestock producers are the most numerous, with 42 respondents (32.1%). Traders, farmers, market gardeners, day labourers and pensioners account for 34 (26%) respectively; 18 (13,7) ; 18 (13,7%) ; 17 (13%) and 2 (1.5%). This shows that almost all peasant people carry out this economic activity.

Like the rest of the country, the village of Konna is mostly illiterate. Despite the policies put in place by the national authorities with the support of partners in the education system with the increase in schools, and the creation of a private high school; The population surveyed is largely illiterate, i.e. 46.6%. Those who have been to school, classical only 3.8% have reached university level; 5.3% have reached secondary level; and 27.5% did not go beyond primary school. As for the respondents who attended the madrasah, they represent 22 respondents, i.e. 16.8%. The population surveyed has a variety of sources of income. However, the sale of livestock remains a lucrative activity for the majority of respondents, i.e. 55%. Traders, farmers, civil servants, and market gardeners represent the population surveyed respectively; 23,7% ; 14,5%, 1,5 % ; and 5.3%.

Table 1: Socio-economic situation of feeders

	Educational attainment	Source of income
Not educated	46.6	x
Primary	27.5	x
Secondary	5.3	x
University	3.8	x
Medarsa	16.8	x
Sale of Agricultural Products	X	14.5
Sale of mouthed cattle	X	55.0
Official	X	1.5
Commerce	X	23.7
Sale of market gardening products	X	5.3

Source: Author's compilation based on the survey

5.2 Characteristics of bovine fattening

The analysis revealed that 106 of the 131 respondents did not have any training on the fattening technique, i.e. 80.9% of the

surveyed population compared to 19.1%. They practice the activity according to information gathered from acquaintances or on intuition. The majority of respondents

“The Contribution of Cattle Fattening to the Improvement of the Living Conditions of Households in the Village of Konna (Mopti)”

carry out this activity on an occasional basis, i.e. 81.7%. Only 13% carry out the fattening activity as a profession; 3.1% for reasons of prestige and 2.3% for reasons of tradition.

We are witnessing different ways in which feeders acquire livestock (Table 2). More than half of the respondents acquire the cattle with their own funds, i.e. 77.9% of the respondents. Financial institutions (banks and microfinance) whose role is to finance the economy are demanding in terms of granting credit. Only 16% of respondents were able to benefit from

bank loans. The rest of the respondents, 6.1%, were able to benefit from the support of the cooperatives that are in place. Cattle are sold at different prices in the local market in Konna. Most feeders buy healthy, young cattle. Of the 131 of the population surveyed, the cattle of the 54 respondents cost between 75,000 and 100,000 CFA francs, i.e. 41.2% of the total population. As for the other respondents; 31.3% paid for livestock ranging from 50,000 to 75,000 FCFA, 26.7% to more than 100,000 FCFA and only 8% of respondents paid for livestock costing less than 50,000 FCFA.

Table 2: Method of acquisition and prices of livestock (in CFA francs)

	Cooperative	Equity	Borrowing from financial institution	Less than 50,000	50.000 - 75.000	75.000- 100.000	More de 100.000
Method of Livestock Acquisition	6,1	77,9	16	x	x	x	x
Livestock prices	x	x	X	8	31,3	41,2	26,7

Source: Author's compilation based on the survey

Cattle feeding remains; the main activity of cattle fattening as the aim is to fatten cattle in order to sell them for a better price. To do this; several foods are involved. Meal is the most used (90.8%), followed by rice bran 89.3%, hay/straw 85.5%; salt 32.1% and corn bran 10.7%.

Personal wells and boreholes remain the main sources of livestock water. They are 64.1% and 22.9% respectively. The public wells and the river are very little used by the mouthwaterers; 9.9% and 3.1%.

The duration of cattle fattening generally depends on the fattening status of the cattle. About 51.1% of respondents keep their cattle between 3 to 4 months; 33.6% within 3 months, and 15.3% between 4 and 6 months.

For the proper operation of the fattening activity, health monitoring is essential. About 93.3% of respondents monitor the health status of their livestock. Follow-up is largely provided by private veterinarians (74%), public veterinarians (9.2%) and mobile veterinarians (16.2%). For this operation, several veterinary products are involved. Including; Oxy 10% is the most used at 67.2%; deworming 58.8%, ivomec 55.0%;

Berenyl 51.9%, and finally disto5 43.5%. Most of its veterinary products are obtained on the local market, i.e. 83.2%. As for the other products, they are bought either outside (9.9%) or with street vendors (6.9%).

5.3- Constraints related to the practice of cattle fattening activity

Like any human activity, the activity of cattle fattening also presents some constraints. The main constraints of the fatteners surveyed vary from the granting of credit, the

purchase of livestock, veterinary follow-up, feeding, maintenance, and the sale of livestock.

The cattle fattening activity begins first with the acquisition of livestock, however 96.9% of respondents believe that they have difficulties in financing financial institutions (banking and microfinance). About 76.3% of respondents are experiencing difficulties in purchasing livestock. As for the difficulties concerning veterinary follow-up, feeding, maintenance and sale; they are respectively 79.4%; 26% ; 73.3% and; 78,6%.

5.4- The impact of cattle fattening on the living conditions of fatteners

The main goal of the cattle fattening business in the village of Konna is to make a profit. What; subsequently, allows them to have a positive impact on their living conditions.

In the search for well-being, the fatteners surveyed affirm that the activity of cattle fattening may have contributed to improving their living conditions in certain areas. Around 31.3% of the population surveyed said that the activity enabled them to cover their medical expenses; 26.7% of respondents said that the activity enabled them to take charge of their children's school supplies; 38.2% saw their mode of dress improved; 10.7% were able to pay their rent; 67.2% saw an improvement in their food; 24.4% were able to carry out other incomegenerating activities; 15.3% had access to safe drinking water; 13.7% had access to electricity, and about 23.7% of respondents were able to sleep under an impregnated mosquito net thanks to the income from the activity.

CONCLUSION

The study provided an understanding of the practice of cattle fattening in the village of Konna. An economic activity that brings well-being for fatteners in several areas. It allowed 41 of the respondents to cover their medical expenses, about 88 of the respondents improved their diet, about 35 respondents were able to pay for their children's school supplies, about 50 respondents were able to improve their clothing, about 14 respondents were able to pay their rent, about 67 respondents saw an improvement in their agricultural productivity, About 32 respondents are engaged in income-generating activities, about 18 respondents have access to safe drinking water, about 20 respondents have access to electricity, and about 31 respondents sleep under an impregnated mosquito net.

However, there are some limitations to cattle fattening. The major constraint that feeders face is financing. The financial institutions that are supposed to finance them are cautious. Training in fattening techniques, veterinary follow-up, and the purchase of cattle are also constraints.

It is important to emphasize that research has not taken into consideration all factors of fattening activity such as vitamins, support from authorities, foreign aid, risk of loss, and risk of death etc. For the well-being of the practitioners, certain factors are not taken into consideration. Transport and communication are factors that the study did not take into account in the living conditions of the feeders. These are factors that can be considered for future research.

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